

ROLE OF EVENT ORGANISING COMPANIES IN INCREASING THE BRAND IMAGE OF THE CLIENT COMPANIES

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ABSTRACT

Event organising is growing at a rate of three times that of traditional advertising. Though relatively small compared to the major components of the marketing communications mix advertising, sales promotions and P-O-P communications-expenditures on event sponsorship are increasing. Corporate sponsorships are offered to various events ranging from sports to festivals to fairs. Thousands of companies invest in some form of event sponsorship. Event organising is a form of brand promotion that ties a brand to a meaningful athletic, entertainment, cultural, social or other type of high-interest public activity. Event organizing is distinct from advertising, sales promotion, point-of-purchase merchandising, or public relations, but it generally incorporates elements from all of these promotional tools. Event promotions have an opportunity to achieve success because, unlike other forms of marketing communications, events reach people when they are receptive to marketing messages and capture people in a relaxed atmosphere. Event organising is growing rapidly because it provides companies alternatives to the cluttered mass media, ability to segment on a local or regional basis, and opportunities for reaching narrow lifestyle groups whose consumption behaviour can be linked with the local event. The need for the study is to analyse certain issues in events organizing and event management, which need further attention. The study uses SPSS for statistical analysis, cross tabulation and chi square for analysing data obtained from structured questionnaire. The study concludes that factors such as quality of service, employee engagement and relationship, use of updated technology, customisation and attracting clients through advertisement and publicity are important factors that determine brand identity of the event management companies.

Key words: Brand Identity, Event management, quality of service, chi square analysis.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Event showcasing is developing at a rate of three times that of customary publicizing. Event showcasing is a type of brand advancement that binds a brand to an important athletic, stimulation, social, social or other kind of high-intrigue open movement. Events along with corporate sponsorship help in showcasing and publicizing, deals etc. Event management for the most part means conceptualizing, fastidious arranging, sorting out lastly executing an occasion or events. It is a set arrangement including systems administration of a mixed media bundle, in this manner accomplishing the customer's destinations and advocating their requirements for taking up with occasions. The event management and showcasing industry is growing at a rate of 17 Percent for every year, and they have accomplished an abnormal state of achievement. Marketing professionals use this as a valuable tool to connect to their existing and potential customers. In the growing era of globalisation, event management professionals are coming out with new ways to engage their customers through trade shows, live events etc. Generating leads and nurturing new customers is becoming the main areas of focus now. Events ranging from formal conferences, brand promotion to corporate parties to music concerts, fashion, sports, high profile weddings and entertainment parties come under the purview of event management companies now. Whole process happens in various stages from preliminary discussions, prefinal talks to articulation and arrangement of stages, visuals, logistics etc.

Events help in brand building, creating awareness about the launch or new products or brand and helping in restoring brands during the distinctive phases of item life cycle, repositioning of brands, associating the brand identify of customers with the identity of target business sector, implementation of marketing plan etc.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Rashid Saeed (2013) this study aims to check the impact of brand picture on brand faithfulness and the directing part of consumer loyalty in the remote telecom division of Pakistan. The study focused on brand properties and brand advantages by surveying around 150 sample respondents who were mainly students and educators from various schools and colleges of Sahiwal. The results obtained from regression and correlation analysis revealed that a positive and noteworthy connection exists between brand picture, brand steadfastness and consumer loyalty. In addition, associations pay more to assemble unique thoughtfulness regarding manufacture the brand picture and to accomplish consumer loyalty.

Baseer Ali Durrani (2015) this study was intended to explain the effect of brand picture on teenager's brand decision and various elements influencing purchasing decision and level of fulfilment from around 300 respondents. The regression results conclude that 33% of the purchase decision and conduct is dependent on commercials, brand picture, promotional tools used by the company. The Pearson relationship demonstrates that adolescents purchasing conduct is fundamentally 36% associated with young people reliability and 49% with notice sway on brand picture. This paper recommends that organizations dealing with products meant for youngsters should focus more on notices, and promotions.

Huseyin Kose (2011) this paper tells that the point of the study was to see the measurements of event administration and event advertising. The investigation of the information was utilized by contextual analysis. They used both essential and optional data (observations, internet, resources, press& visual media). This paper concentrates on the measurements of occasion administration named ticketing, transportation, HR (volunteers and prepared staff) planning, advertising and PR and danger administration. By and large the study finds that the most critical thing is to oversee hazard administration measurement where administrators ought to do chance administration well by occasion ambulances, medicinal groups and security staff constantly prepared.

Fransisca Andreani (2012) this paper advises that the fundamental target is to look at the effect of brand picture towards client devotion with consumer loyalty as a go between. The study used Partial Least Square (PLS) and results demonstrate that there is a positive effect of quality of brand affiliation towards client steadfastness, consumer loyalty and consumer loyalty towards client faithfulness.

3. RESEARCH DESIGN

3.1. Statement of the Problem

Event organizers play a vital role in creating & improving the brand image of the companies where in few organizers are not producing the quality of the brand that is necessary for the company & it does not add any value by that event so now a day's corporate clients are very much curious of selecting the event organizers who are very good & they view that it adds value & maintain the standards of creating the brand image of the company by organizing the event successfully. Hence this study is taken up in order to know the role of event management companies in boosting the brand image of client companies.

3.2. Objectives of the Study

- To understand the concepts of event organizing its benefits & implementation process in various events of different companies
- To evaluate the effectiveness of event organizing as a promotional tool to the company brand image
- To offer suggestions for improvement to make it a more productive investment for the company by organising the event this adds value & benefits of the company.

3.3. Hypothesis

H0: Price of successful events and Brand Identity of successful events are independent of each other.

H1: Price of successful events and Brand Identity of successful events are dependent of each

Other

H0: Employee relations of successful events and Brand Identity of successful events are independent of each other.

H1: Employee relations of successful events and Brand Identity of successful events are dependent of each other

H0: Unique of successful events and Attracting customers of successful events are independent of each other.

H1: Unique of successful events and Attracting customers of successful events are dependent of each other

H0: Employee relations of successful events and Attracting customers of successful events are independent of each other.

H1: Employee relations of successful events and Attracting customers of successful events are dependent of each other

H0: Technology building brand and event organising companies benefited to clients are independent of each other

H1: Technology building brand and event organising companies benefited to clients are dependent of each other

H0: Publicity building brand and event organising companies benefited to clients are independent of each other

H1: Publicity building brand and event organising companies benefited to clients are dependent of each other

3.4. Sampling

The study will be restricted to Bangalore city. The sample size consists of 60 respondents involving employees and corporate clients. Convenient sampling method has been used for this research.

3.5. Sources of Data

The data for the study was obtained from detailed discussions with event management firms and the corporate clients. Subsequent additions were made to the interview schedule to suit the specific events under study and also from various marketing journals and books on event marketing, sales promotions and publicity.

3.6. Analysis

The research is both exploratory and descriptive in nature and relies on both primary and secondary data. Data collected from the structured questionnaire will be processed using SPSS software and MS-Excel. The processed data will be analysed for Mean, Chi-square, and Correlation.

4. DATA ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

It is evident from the above analysis that 50% of the respondents belongs to the age group of 30-40 years. 30% of the respondents came to know about event organising companies by event organisers. It is evident from the above analysis that 67% of the respondents have organised the events and about 30% of the respondents have organised events more frequently after a year and agree that 43% of the respondents have been satisfied by the event organisers in completing the event successfully and are able to increase brand value to their client companies and quality in services help build positive brand image. It is evident from the above analysis that 46.7% of the respondents have agreed that technology help build a positive brand image to the client companies by the event organisers. It is evident from the above analysis that 40% of the respondents have been agreed where advertisement help build a positive brand image to the client companies by the event organisers. Event organisers can satisfy their client through products and services according to the specific occasion and specifications given by their clients and they plan the events based on the budget and price affordability of the clients.

4.1. Table Showing KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin	Measure of Sampling	.679
Adequacy.		
Bartlett's	Approx. Chi-Square	138.963
Test	of	
Sphericity	df	36
	Sig.	.000

The KMO & Bartlett's test conforms that test conducted is adequate & can be used for identifying the various variable & attributes at 15% level of significance

4.2. Table Showing Communalities Test

	Initial	Extraction
wedding party are the event you organise more frequently	1.000	.798
corporate events are the event you organise more frequently	1.000	.835
sports events are the event you organise more frequently	1.000	.789
product launch are the event you organise more frequently	1.000	.716

		.791
concerts are the event you organise more frequently	1.000	
live shows are the event you organise more frequently	1.000	.822
fashion shows are the event you organise more frequently	1.000	.878
birthday parties are the event you organise more frequently	1.000	.634
celebrity parties are the event you organise more frequently	1.000	.800
Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.		

4.3. Table Showing Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	Cronbach's Alpha Based on Standardized Items	No of Items
.610	.630	8

Cronbach alpha is tested to establish the consistency of the instrument which is used to collect the data. Most of the constructs are more than .6 and some are more than 0.7 which shows that the instrument is very much consistent. The respondents have provided consistent response to the items of the concerned constructs.

Cross tabulation and chi square test were used in order to establish relationship between various variables used in the study and to test the above mentioned hypotheses. Through Chi square analysis, the study establishes that quality of successful events and brand identity of successful events, advertisement building brand image and benefit to client companies through event management companies, entertainment for successful events and brand identity, price for successful events and attracting customers for successful events are independent of each other. Brand identity and several factors such as price of successful events, employee relationship in success of events, uniqueness of successful events, attracting customers towards the event management companies, relevance of technology in brand building are dependent on each other.

4.4. Correlation Coefficient of Factors Preferred By the Client Companies on Five Different Dimensions

		D2	D4	D5	D7	D10
D1	Pearson Correlation	.442*	.506**	.486**	.431*	.385*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.014	.004	.006	.017	.036
	N	30	30	30	30	30

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed) **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

As per the above table, the correlations of D1 (factors preferred by the client companies) with all the five analyzed dimensions (i.e. D2 (factors noticed or participated in the event), D4 (factors fulfilled by the event organising companies), D5 (organising events frequently), D7(types of events organised) and D10(factors to understand and satisfy the company clients) are found to be positive and significant (at 5% and 1% level). It indicates that more and more of D1 cues help in identifying the brand more easily, more

quickly attract the brand value of clients, faster brand recognition, increase of probability of increasing the brand value and so on. However, observing the correlation values, it shows that the relationship between D1 cue and dimensions such as D2, D4, D5, D7 and D10 is moderate.

4.5. Correlation Coefficient of Factors Noticed or Participated in the Event on Three Different Dimensions

		D1	D4	D5
D2	Pearson Correlation	.442*	.515**	.398*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.014	.004	.030
	N	30	30	30

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed) **. significant at 0.01

As per the above table, the correlations of D2 (factors noticed or participated in the event in client perspective) with all the three analyzed dimensions (i.e. D1 (factors preferred by the client companies), D4 (factors fulfilled by the event organising companies), and D5 (organising events frequently) are found to be positive and significant (at 5% and 1% level). It indicates that more and more of D2 cues help in identifying the brand more easily, more quickly attract the brand value of clients, faster brand recognition, increase of probability of increasing the brand value and so on. However, observing the correlation values, it shows that the relationship between D2 cue and dimensions such as D1, D4 and D5 is moderate.

4.6. Correlation Coefficient of Factors Fulfilled By the Event Organising Companies on Four Different Dimensions

		D1	D2	D5	D10
D4	Pearson Correlation	.506**	.515**	.422*	.586**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.004	.004	.020	.001
	N	30	30	30	30

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level

As per the above table, the correlations of D4 (factors fulfilled by the event organising companies) with all the four analyzed dimensions (i.e. D1(factors preferred by the client companies) D2(factors noticed or participated in the event in client perspective), D5 (organising events frequently) and D10 (factors to understand and satisfy the company clients) are found to be positive and significant (at 5% and 1% level). It indicates that more and more of D4 cues help in identifying the brand more easily, more quickly attract the brand value of clients, faster brand recognition, increase of probability of increasing the brand value and so on. However, observing the correlation values, it shows that the relationship between D4 cue and dimensions such as D1, D2, D5 and D10 is high.

4.7. Correlation Coefficient of Organising Events Frequently on Four Different Dimensions

		D1	D2	D4	D6
D5	Pearson Correlation	.486**	.398*	.422*	.407*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.006	.030	.020	.026
	N	30	30	30	30

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed) **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

As per the above table, the correlations of D5 (organising events frequently) with all the four analyzed dimensions (i.e. D1 (factors preferred by the client companies), D2 (factors noticed or participated in the event in client perspective), D4 (factors fulfilled by the event organising companies) and D6 (factors noticed or participated in the event in company perspective) are found to be positive and significant (at 5% and 1% level). It indicates that more and more of D5 cues help in identifying the brand more easily, more quickly attract the brand value of clients, faster brand recognition, increase of probability of increasing the brand value and so on. However, observing the correlation values, it shows that the relationship between D5 cue and dimensions such as D1, D2, D4 and D6 is moderate.

4.8. Correlation Coefficient of Factors Noticed or Participated in the Event in Company Perspective on Two Different Dimensions

		D5	D10
D6	Pearson Correlation	.407*	-.374*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.026	.042
	N	30	30

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed) **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

As per the above table, the correlations of D6 (factors noticed or participated in the event in company perspective) with all the two analyzed dimensions (i.e. D5 (organising events frequently) and D10 (factors to understand and satisfy the company clients) are found to be positive and significant (at 5% and 1% level). It indicates that more and more of D6 cues help in identifying the brand more easily, more quickly attract the brand value of clients, faster brand recognition, increase of probability of increasing the brand value and so on. However, observing the correlation values, it shows that the relationship between D6 cue and dimensions such as D5 and D10 is moderate.

4.9. Correlation Coefficient of Types of Events Organised on Three Different Dimensions

		D1	D8	D9
D7	Pearson Correlation	.431*	.539**	.468**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.017	.002	.009
	N	30	30	30

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed) **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

As per the above table, the correlations of D7 (types of events organised) with all the three analyzed dimensions (i.e. D1 (factors preferred by the client companies), D8 (factors mostly preferred in successful event) and D9 (To build positive brand image)) are found to be positive and significant (at 5% and 1% level). It indicates that more and more of D7 cues help in identifying the brand more easily, more quickly attract the brand value of clients, faster brand recognition, increase of probability of increasing the brand value and so on. However, observing the correlation values, it shows that the relationship between D7 cue and dimensions such as D1, D8 and D9 is moderate.

4.10. Correlation Coefficient of Factors Mostly Preferred in Successful Event on Three Different Dimensions

		D7	D9
D8	Pearson Correlation	.539**	.502**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.002	.005
	N	30	30

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed) **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

As per the above table, the correlations of D8 (factors mostly preferred in successful event) with all the two analyzed dimensions (i.e. D7(types of events organised) and D9(To build positive brand image)) are found to be positive and significant (at 5% and 1% level). It indicates that more and more of D8 cues help in identifying the brand more easily, more quickly attract the brand value of clients, faster brand recognition, increase of probability of increasing the brand value and so on. However, observing the correlation values, it shows that the relationship between D8 cue and dimensions such as D7 and D9 is high.

4.11. Correlation Coefficient of to Build Positive Brand Image on Two Different Dimensions

		D7	D8
D9	Pearson Correlation	.468**	.502**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.009	.005
	N	30	30

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed) **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

As per the above table, the correlations of D9 (To build positive brand image) with all the two analyzed dimensions (i.e. D7 (types of events organised) and D8 (factors mostly preferred in successful event)) are found to be positive and significant (at 5% and 1% level). It indicates that more and more of D9 cues help in identifying the brand more easily, more quickly attract the brand value of clients, faster brand recognition, increase of probability of increasing the brand value and so on. However, observing the correlation values, it shows that the relationship between D9 cue and dimensions such as D7 and D8 is moderate.

4.12. Correlation Coefficient of Factors to Understand and Satisfy the Company Clients on Three Different Dimensions

		D1	D4	D6
D10	Pearson Correlation	.385*	.586**	-.374*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.036	.001	.042
	N	30	30	30

*. Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed) **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed)

As per the above table, the correlations of D10 (factors to understand and satisfy the company clients) with all the three analyzed dimensions (i.e. D1(factors preferred by the client companies), D4(factors

fulfilled by the event organising companies) and D6(factors noticed or participated in the event in company perspective) are found to be positive and significant (at 5% and 1% level). It indicates that more and more of D10 cues help in identifying the brand more easily, more quickly attract the brand value of clients, faster brand recognition, increase of probability of increasing the brand value and so on. However, observing the correlation values, it shows that the relationship between D10 cue and dimensions such as D1, D4 and D6 is moderate.

5. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

It is evident from the above analysis that 50% of the respondents belong to the age group of 30-40. Majority of the respondents have organised events on their own and later have outsourced some events to event management companies and are satisfied about the success of the event and have agreed that event organisers are able to increase brand value to their client companies. The brand identity through advertising and publicity and use of updated technology is mostly preferred by the client companies to the organising event companies for the successful events. An event can be made successful only by proper planning and execution so as to deliver highest quality service to clients. The KMO & Bartlett's test conforms that test conducted is adequate & can be used for identifying the various variable & attributes at 15% level of significance. The Pearson Chi-Square has established independency of variables such as quality and brand identity, entertainment and brand identity. But factors such as price and brand identity, employee relationship and delivery of quality service, technology and quality of service and satisfaction of customers are dependent on each other. Uniqueness of service rendered is also considered as an important factor in attracting customers towards event management companies.

6. CONCLUSION

This research has been taken to study the value of brand improvement by the event management company to their clients. The study shows that maintaining their quality, providing good services, improvising on the brand quality of their clients and moreover satisfying the customers' needs and fulfilling them are very relevant for success of event management companies and building their brand identity. Event management companies can initiate promotion, advertising and use upgraded technology and provide quality of service at competitive price to customers. The issues encountered by the clients given in the form of feedback should be dealt with earnest efforts from the company. Consistent service quality should be provided by the company to maintain the reputation of the company and to have long term relationship. Each event should be taken care as individual identity and thorough planning and execution should be made. Any suggestions given by the clients should be processed systematically in order to overcome the flaws and improve the customer service. Quality dimension such as cleanliness, hygiene, arrangements, security and safety should be given top priority. Employee relationship should be given top priority. Only with good employee engagement long term relationship with the clients and customers can be maintained. Company can have training sessions for employees in the areas of client management, negotiations, use of technology etc.

REFERENCE

- [1] Church, R. and C. Clark (2003) 'Purposive strategy or serendipity? Development and diversification in three consumer product companies, 1918-39: J. & J. Colman, Reckitt & Son, and Lever Bros./Unilever', *Business History*, 45 (1): 23-59.
- [2] Cano, C (2003) 'The recent evolution of market segmentation concepts and thoughts primarily by marketing academics', in E. Shaw (ed) *The romance of marketing history: proceedings of the 11th Conference on Historical Analysis and Research in Marketing (CHARM)*. Boca Ranton, FL: AHRIM, 2003.
- [3] Arvidsson, A. (2006) *Brands: meaning and value in media culture*, Abingdon, Oxon: Routledge.

- [4] Davies, A. and R. Elliot (2006) 'The evolution of the empowered consumer', *European Journal of Marketing* 40 (9/10): 1106-1121.
- [5] Stefan Schwarzkopf (2008) *Turning Trade Marks into Brands: how Advertising Agencies Created Brands in the Global Market Place, 1900-1930.*
- [6] Akanshu Verma, Ankit Mandawat, Rachit Kuchhal and Robin Jindal, A Customer Centric Brand Analysis of IPL Using Brand Molecule Tool . *International Journal of Management (IJM)* , 7 (5), 201 6 , pp. 58 – 66
- [7] Ela Kumari, Gauhar Fatma (2014) *Branding: An Indispensable Strategy for Product Marketing*, *International Journal Of Management Research*, Volume -2, Issue -12.
- [8] *Administration and showcasing challenges for the information Society* (2012) Vol.7, No 4, pp.759-776.
- [9] *European Scientific Journal* February 2015 edition Vol.11, No.5ISSN:1857–7881 ISSN 1857-7431 **IMPACT OF BRAND IMAGE ON BUYINGBEHAVIOUR AMONG TEENAGERS** Baseer Ali Durrani, Danish Iqbal Godil, Mirza Uzair Baig.
- [10] Fransisca Andreani, Tan Lucy Taniaji and Ruth Natalia Made Puspitasari Vol.14, NO. 1, Maret 2012: 63–70.
- [11] Dr. K. Abdus Samad and M. Sabeerdeen. A Study on Effective Brand Promotional Strategies Influencing Customers. *International Journal of Management (IJM)*, 7 (2), 2016, pp. 52 - 65 .
- [12] *Uncommon occasion administration and occasion advertising* *Diary of Management and Marketing Research*(2011)
- [13] Huseyin Kose (Anadolu), Mehpare Tokay Argan, Metin Argan *World Applied Sciences Journal* 26 (10): 1364-1370, 2013 ISSN 1818-4952© IDOSI Publications, 2013 Rashid Saeed, Rab Nawaz Lodhi, Amna Mehmood, Urooj Ishfaque, Fareha Dustgeer, Amna Sami, Zahid Mahmood and Moeed Ahmad